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Production of Nano Cellulose in Miniature-Bioreactor: Optimization and Characterization

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Abstract

Bacterial Cellulose (BC) is a very fascinating microbial biopolymer which is mainly produced by *Gluconacetobacter xylinum*. Optimization of BC production by *G. xylinum* was carried out based on scale-down studies in miniature-bioreactor and response surface methodology in which the optimum pH value (6.5) and shaking rate (50rpm) were obtained. The static culture condition for BC production has newly been defined. Nano-structure of BC includes nano-fibers up to (60nm) and nano-porosity up to (265nm) was observed by SEM. By FTIR study, the most expected BC interaction is nucleophilic interaction. MTT assay showed high biocompatibility. Appropriate mechanical strength (0.37 MPa) and young's modulus (3.36MPa) evinced BC scaffold utilization for skin tissue. The results indicate that BC sheets can be utilized in biomedical application and nanotechnology approaches.

KEYWORDS: Bacterial Cellulose, *Gluconacetobacter xylinum*, Static culture, Optimization, Miniature-bioreactor.